

200 100 0 200 km

▲ archaeological site
 — border
 — river
 ● capital
 COUNTRY

DEM: Natural Earth 2 v3.2
 Admin: The World Bank
 Hydro: Natural Earth, OSM

Projection: WGS 1984
 Datum: WGS 1984

